

- Robert Burke - The Electric Universe - Younger Dryas Implications
- https://math.ucr.edu/home/baez/diary/november_2009.html
- <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016E&PSL.437..127R/abstract>

MESS 0036

Responding to R. Burke's Himalaya-Comet YDE Hypothesis; a flaw in macrolytics, aka why you must do field research in EGM altstream theory

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the author examines a snippet of a longer conversation held between amateur electrogeologist, Robert Burke, and trained geologist turned electrogeologist, “Diamond.” Bob Burke is a respectable gentleman who recently spoke at the 2022 World Expo which the author attended and spoke at¹. But this video was shocking, and the author wishes to make clear that Diamond is 100% correct about the lack of physical evidence for Burke’s assertions about the Himalaya “strike” hypothesis. Through an examination of statements, the author wishes to also discuss the philosophical importance in EPEMC of following an empirical scientific method, as a standard, as well as a guidepost for EGM. It is not permissible for the altstream to allow anything less than this standard, with or without peer review is *irrelevant*. The facts call for the highest standards of examination, and logic. Burke’s hypothesis has little to no basis, but the greater issue is that without any gradation or standards, hypotheses like this, Zamora’s, or Corsetti’s² are capable of confusing millions of seekers and altstream adherents. As the saying goes, “out of the frying pan, and into the fire.” This problem is not a solution to the Science Delusion, Scientism, or the lies of the mainstream, and its many coverups and distortions of medicine and scientific fact!

Keywords: Tarim Basin - Taklamakan - Himalayas - Venus - Near Impact - Comet - Tektites

¹ 2022 EM World Expo - Shifu Ramon part 1 / Extended Plasma Electromagnetic Cosmology EPEMC

² https://www.academia.edu/63468751/Ashes_of_Atlantis_part_1

Timestamped Claims

Robert Burke:

1. 2:45-3:10 - Mississippi and Amazon rivers being lichtenburgs
2. 3:35 - "the current will create a circuit."
3. 3:43 - we live in an Electric Universe; the cataclysm itself is encoded in mythology across the planet
4. 4:05 - identifying that Venus was the celestial object that we had a near impact with.
5. 4:10 - that's why I begin with the near impact site in the Himalayan Tarim Basin (sic)
6. 4:30 - an unsourced but cited paper lays out what a meteor impact "should look like."
7. 4:54 - what you should get is a round, cone surface, a peak apex if it was moving, and a long streak pattern if it came in at an angle.
8. 5:15 - the only reason no one has looked at this area and not identified it as a "near impact" site is the sheer size of it.
9. 5:40 - and that mark is the Himalayan mountains and the tarim basin left in the middle
10. 5:55 - Mt. Everest is in the rim of what I am claiming to be the near impact site; and if it is you should find the highest/most extraordinary point on the planet.

Diamond:

11. 6:05 - This is a great theory but the only problem is that all of the Younger Dryas impact proxies... none of them are found in this region. There's a region called the YD impact field, ... [shares screen]
12. 6:40 - now all the incidents of nano-diamonds, micro-spherules, tektites... multiple types of nano-diamonds: lonsdaleite, magnetic grains, shocked quartz, and every single impactor... showing up at 12,8[00 YBP] +/- 20 [years] only within this YD impact field. None of them are within the Himalayas. In fact these researchers went across the entire globe and ... took samples of these stratigraphies... and found none of them. [He then asks his sources if he has no impactor minerals.]
13. 7:40 - If you're working off of Velikovsky, [he] said specifically that Venus was ejected out of Jupiter around 2,000 BC and then made two close fly-bys near on Earth around 1,500 BC, which is nowhere near the YD Event.

Bob:

14. 8:00 - yeah well, outside of the fact that the story of Atlantis places the cataclysm at about the same period, I'm really skeptical of the 12kya event, in part because that's just a lot of years to go through; ... I don't have to get tied up on an exact year that it happened.

Diamond:

15. 8:25 - the sinking of Atlantis occurs at the 11,5[00 YBP], which is exactly the end of the YD, which is when the sea level rose 330'

Bob:

16. 8:40 - yeah well when we look at the ice core data... one of the things we have to look at, specifically, is... well let's start with your diagram; so what I'd like you to know about this diagram... is the Eastern side of the diagram is it leads directly up in front of the NIS.
17. 9:10 - so if you know anything about electricity, is that charge, that is the thing that people call the positive side... is going one direction in the circuit, while the current is moving the other direction in the circuit, which is showing you the direction of energy moving, which is not in the direction you think it

is... is in the opposite direction [of the moviement]... from west to east because that's the direction the current was flowing in the cataclysm.

18. 9:45 - this is an example of a sail, and I'm a sailor, and one of the things you learn about sails, and if you fly, you learn the same thing about a wing, right? So a sail or a wing does not work because air is pushed into the front... into the sail. Not you're pushed along, the wind hits the sail, and along the front side of the sail creates low pressure, and that hauls the boat along. What this is showing you is the "pull" of that material from the cataclysm itself.

Leah Shaper

19. 10:30 - one of the things we'd need to address is if we are looking at the Himalyas do we have any geological data from when that happened.
20. 10:43 - is your proposal that Venus actually hit Earth or that it was a plasma contact?

Bob:

21. 10:50 - so I have always used the term that it was a Near Impact, and the reason is... twofold. One: when we're talking about an Electric Universe, everything is scalable. Whatever is true at the smallest level is also true at the largest level. In real physics nothing ever really touches each other. ... That's just kind of a really common fact that people don't know. So... when a ball bounces off the ground, it doesn't bounce, it is reflected off the ground by a force called self-capacitance... the energy is absorbed and re-transformed back to the ball, causing it to bounce off... etc. all of that processes electric in Nature, and we know that... etc.
22. 11:55 - that everything is electric has long been established and so any change in direction would be electric in nature... we're back in "everything is electric" explanation, and all the elements we have to tell it... is electric in nature... if you've ever played golf, near impact event.

Leah:

23. 12:26 - yeah I get that... so I guess the question would be what is the force that formed this 'crater' and again I think we need some geological information ... Diamond do you know anything about this 'crater'?

Bob:

24. 12:40 - Absolutely... it is fascinating and odd things about this area that further confirm an electric in nature electric event; for example in the Tarim Basin itself, geologists have no idea why but the entire ground has been moved and turned 45 degrees... it might be 26... in any case the whole ground turned counter-clockwise... I want to say about 30 degrees. That turning is what happens when a charge goes in the ground. The charge rotates an inductive force in a counter-clockwise manner. The charge went into the Earth as it was NEAR IMPACT... nearing impact with the Earth. That's the nature of electricity (sic)
25. 13:36 - the other thing it did was create a HUGE amount of what they call "micro-plates." There's also a giant bolus of a silicon and ridges underneath that are all ... like a bowl. And they think "well this must have been a sea somewhere in the past. It wasn't a sea... in electrical arcing, these are very normal layerings that occurred during the exchange of energy. Once again we're using standard electric terminology. Things that are used everyday in manufacturing. "Bob what does this look like?" the TB looks like an electrical discharge crater.

26. 14:16 - One of the other interesting things is that we KNOW that there is a connection between the um south Atlantic oscillations, and the amount of rain that'll happen up in the TB,... the Himalayan Mountains, it's called the SA oscillation. So how do you get an oscillation that picks up the ocean all the way up in the TB? The answer is that those two are *linked* by the event. The TB was the high pressure location for the impact ... and the SA is the low impact... low pressure zone on the other side; that is the sail sucking from the surface out.

Leah:

27. 15:00 - so if we were to link this basin to the YD impact zone, is this essentially you're proposing that the material found in the YD impact zone was *thrown* in from this position?

Bob:

28. 15:20 - yeah well in front of it... If you want to go in closer you can see in front of the image, that what you're really dealing with is... a golf ball hitting the ground on the green, and if they have a lot of spin which they both did, it will kick up a lot of grass in front of it. Well that's the nature of ... a meteor impact, and there's a study out there that talks about what it looks like... and you should have ejecta to the front side.

Diamond:

29. 15:45 - the huge problem here is that there's no evidence that this is an impact. None, geologically. In fact, this basin is referred to as one of the largest petroleum repositories on Earth. So it's a sedimentary basin that had subsequent *huge* magmatic episodes. These are what the pyroclastic flows around the periphery consist of. It's dated at Tertiary, meaning it was deposited millions and millions of years ago. ... So it's a... flat lying basin that has been undisturbed, and in fact the exact OPPOSITE of an impact site. Not only that there are no [impactors] and no evidence of any impact in this region anywhere.

Bob:

30. 16:33 - Like I said, the issue most people have is that they can't imagine an event this large. If you scroll back up...

Diamond:

31. 16:43 - [unintelligible] .. impact zone, so imagining one this large doesn't matter. You need evidence of an impact.

Bob:

32. 16:50 - so if you'll scroll up a little bit further, let's look at the broader area... and if you do you'll notice that you have the elongated cratering that you would have if a ball were coming in.

Diamond:

33. 17:10 - you're talking... your evidence is a shape; that is what a third grader would say. You need to have cosmogenic evidence; you need radionuclides; you need shocked quartz; you need micro-tektites. None of these are in this region... Even if you're claiming Venus is in close proximity and there is plasma discharging we would have ALL of this... we would have all of the discharge proxies that we see in the YD basin. We see an increase in Beryllium-10; only formed in cosmic space, raining down on this region. Why aren't they raining down on this region?

It only continued to go downhill from here, with bad behavior, scientifically speaking, from Bob.

Author's Responses

1. I've seen this claim before; and it is **incorrect**. There are distinct differences to the trained eye between the angles and curvature in fluvial systems and lichtenburbs. This is covered in my trip reports and topics covering the Knobs Region, which is a classic lichtenburg³. You can tell the difference visually and geologically, macroscopically and microscopically, between the Knobs anode formation and the carved fluvial regions immediately surrounding it.
2. That's backwards innit?
3. On its face this is a fine statement; but it's a *plasma-electromagnetic* Universe, to be precise.
4. Maybe, but maybe not only. The best evidence is the Richat and the sands of the Sahara, based on my examination of the compositions⁴. However, it isn't 1:1 and in the end we don't know how these sands could be transformed under atmospheric conditions.
5. A priori fallacy?
6. This is valuable, but comes back to bite him in the ass *after* he was shalacked; The thing is Diamond is right. What things look like is far less important, in a system of self-similarity and fractality, than what their suchness is.
7. Okay, the things he is saying here have validity, however, it works against him. See:

Figure 1 - Himalaya regions; as you can see vector A doesn't match the proposed bowshock of vector

³ MESS0028: GEO 2.24 - Proposed Electrogeological Scales

⁴ "Ashes" Ibid., Appendix B, Table 2

B; even a third grader could see this if explained. The blue arc is supportive of crustal uplift and not blast coming from the Tarim basin.

8. Well, that's not the only reason. I actually do think that the Tarim Basin is the result of cataclysm, just not the kind hypothesised. Or not anytime recently.
9. See Figure 1
10. I will grant that it is unusual that the FRONT of the Indian/Asian impact of plates being higher than the back end is rather weird; but the proposal by the mainstream is that it was happening rather fast, geologically, and this led to a rapid buildup. The fact that Everest and K-2 are still growing⁵ supports this, and does not support the VNI hypothesis.

11. Figure 2 - the YDB Field; credit: phys.org

Please note that the field happens to be in regions that are freer, safer to study, and more samples have been taken; and may *not* be comprehensive. Likely not. However, that nothing shows up in China, when they have plenty of scientists... is probably supportive of Diamond, and not of Bob.

12. Yes, in my [limited] experience, what Diamond says here is 100% correct. We find it in Kentucky, Australia, the desert Southwest, etc.
13. He's a bit off, here. The Venus event⁶ was around 2,400-2,600 BC, but the point is moot and stays the same.
14. This is a *massive* tactical mistake in the argument; reading through the basically warm audience, he lost several viewers with this. Again, the imprecision is an issue. The precision of the Atlantis myth with the carbon dating⁷ is useful against the mainstream lies and Lying Liars. Why abandon it? This only makes one an island, sinking himself in an ocean of argument.
15. Er... that period of time, though, was only ~85 feet. The majority of the rise began well before in the meltwater pulse A₀.

Figure 3 - Rise in sea level

⁵ <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20220407-how-tall-will-mount-everest-get-before-it-stops-growing>

⁶ "World's in Collision," Dr. Velikovsky, 1950

⁷ Joe Rogan Experience #872 - Graham Hancock & Randall Carlson

- 16. Eh, not really. There's a good gap between the two of thousands of miles.
- 17. The vibration of this is a bit condescending.

However, let's just look at the statement. It's clear that Diamond's body language switched to attack mode, once he felt it was a literal you and not the universal, plural you. Bob misjudged his audience and place. Nevertheless, the question is, is this true?

Sort of. There is a transmutation or rearrangement of minerals on the end of the *discharge*, because energy is being sequestered on the other end where charge flows.

Figure 4 - Lithium ion battery motion of charge and discharge; deposition definitely accrues on one electrode.

- 18. Literally non-sequitur.
- 19. Leah is 100% correct.
- 20. It is probably a plasma and sand discharge region; but it didn't create the Himalayas. However, Venus did uplift **these** mountains in the Patagonia; Figure 5:

- 21. At this point, it is clear that Bob has lost the plot and been thrown for a loop. He was either ill-prepared or unprepared; either way he "misunderestimated" Diamond and Leah, to quote "W". The issue is that this argument is not clear, and makes no sense, and is ambiguous.
- 22. While I agree; unfortunately the majority of the science community is deluded and would strongly disagree with this point. The remainder of the statement is vague and difficult; and improbable.
- 23. She is being kind here. Honey, just tell him that made no sense. That's what Diamond and the audience are thinking.

24. See point 21. The way this turned was interesting, it seems he's trying to talk about counter rotation? But the exact condensation it ended with was probably a disastrous mistake, because Leah is Diamond's girl, AND she has talking to Diamond to get her confusion clarified... and Bob shat out this almost unintelligible, ill prepared statement. From here we see the disaster is imminent. The cataclysm isn't going to be near impact; Bob's ego is about to be impacted by Comet Diamond.

25. Figure 6: He appears to be talking about this map; credit: Y Li et al.⁸

But let's use:

Figure 7 - The Tarim Basin fault zones; credit: L. Jiang⁹

⁸ <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feart.2021.792049/full>

⁹ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319709841_Diagenesis_of_an_evaporite-related_carbonate_reservoir_in_deeply_buried_Cambrian_strata_Tarim_Basin_Northwest_China/figures?lo=1

- Looking at this, I think an impact vector is possible; only the evidence either hasn't yet been found, or it was washed away. It's also possible that the region was excavated as a cathode, and the even was so thorough the evidence was removed; or buried thoroughly. But at this time, it is definitely unlikely.
26. Definitely some *a priori* statement. He is guessing at this, I am certain.
 27. He wasn't, but now he is. I think it's possible, but the evidence at present is either inconclusive or conclusive against.
 28. This is a bizarre argument, but we'll just have to imagine the YD field being thrown from the area up to the area from the TB.
 29. At this point Diamond shows him the extent of his formal training and knowledge of the region is, if rusty, still precise and greater than that of R. Burke.
 30. This was a massive, and disrespectful, mistake. At this point, 3 major mistakes, and ill preparation... means an imminent collapse of discourse, which is heading to conflict and debate.
 31. Diamond is right, and wrong here. Actually the energy levels *do matter*, and I've explained to Bob before on "the Electric View" that he was having a problem of seeing energy scales at smaller scales, regarding the Great Lakes Formation hypothesis he promotes.¹⁰ He is right, though; there should be some kind of evidence. Sadly, if excavated by electrogravity, "lack of evidence" is not itself evidence. The mainstream deludes itself with this with Cold Dark Matter, all the time. I've literally seen peer reviewed papers with this argument.¹¹
 32. See Figure 1. Bob failed a basic test here. The vectors of A and B do not match.
 33. Here's the moment that Diamond "breaks his back." This argument should probably have ended it. Unfortunately the dance goes one ranging around bullcrap and placating egos. It's not worth continuing from here. Diamond has dunked on him, and it's just like Figure 8:

Blake Griffth posterizing; credit: NBA

How Electrogeology *Should* Be Done

The standards¹² of science, and the scientific method *do not change* because one is in the altstream. Mostly, science is about debunking bad hypotheses, or wrong theories, and testing the strength of scientific laws. After that, it is difficult to prove anything, so what you do is pile up mountains of evidence in order to make statistical proof of the hypotheses you are testing, while continuously

¹⁰ [YouTube: The Electric View - Electric Landscapes - TEV Live](#)

¹¹

https://www.academia.edu/38105102/The_Dark_Matter_Scatter_How_the_Dark_Universe_Community_is_fraying_and_in_which_directions_as_a_response_to_the_DM_crisis How PEMC re unifies the camps

https://www.academia.edu/53147237/Response_to_New_Dark_Energy

¹² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

introducing stricter and stricter controls. You do this for three reasons:

1. To enable a repeatable experiment or test for others to verify your work.
2. To ensure that correlative reasoning doesn't taint the results with nearly correct, or confused theorems that conflate the issues and facts.
3. To remove the possibilities of contamination as potentials, and also to remove the un-necessary aspects of the hypothesis that are not exactly the right information.

When validating predictions, it is important to base them on something to start with; and when doing the studies and trip reports, it is important to keep track of results, evidence, data, and information.

In write ups, as always with EPEMC, you need to cite your evidence. At minimum as I do as an engineer, list links. Up to peer review or APA style citation. But something has to be cited, and one's work needs to not stand alone, or contain logic errors, a priori assumptions,^{13 14}

The Importance of Surveying and Field Trips

Not leaving the house and making lots of theories is, to say the least, problematic. One time the AKHA did a site survey for a site that, on LiDAR, had what appeared to be a hitherto unknown serpent mound. Not impossible, because archaeologists have been finding new sites with KY From Above since 2017. So, we went to the site (one of the late Bruce Grimes' contacts), and hoofed it. The terrain was *so similar* to that of the Russellville "lost city" that the author and Grimes thought it was certainly going somewhere. But nothing was to be found. After speaking with the local owners and people we met, it was learned that the area had once held a now vanished town. The curvature was old logging roads, and nothing like hidden walls or serpents. There was something interesting, historically, from the 20th century but it was all gone, now.

The field trips¹⁵ are necessary to verify what you see. On the author's second visit to the Garden of the Gods, is when he discovered the A++ electrogeology evidence, as shown in the trip report¹⁶. Often sites need more than one visit; and even then you might not get lucky. The verification of the Dogfoot Hollow Wall at the Pebble Beach Wall, was a stroke of pure luck, but was an extension of the Hidden Destination Kentucky¹⁷ project. "You never know, til you go."

What Constitutes Empirical Evidence, Data, and Proof

Empirical means it is actually observed. Not observed as CGI, simulation, or through satellite imagery. Evidence is any information, but data can be measured, re-measured, compared statistically, or used to validate against other data sets. Proof requires more than a 5% or even 1% difference or error; it requires a less than 1% difference, preferably less than 0.1% and a very low sigma in terms of standard deviation or other equivalent statistic. When a coincidence is below one in twelve million, it can be considered a 0% chance in engineering; and below 1 in 20 million will be considered a 0% chance and scientific proof within a more than reasonable standard. These will constitute what we call A+++ or Platinum standard evidence in PEMC.

¹³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer>

¹⁴

https://www.academia.edu/37569958/EPEMC_tm_Benefits_Ten_Reasons_to_Consider_Switching_to_Extended_Plasma_electromagnetic_Cosmology

¹⁵ [MESS0035: A Guide to the EPEMC Trip Reports](#)

¹⁶ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

¹⁷ www.hiddendestinationsky.com

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|-------------|----------|--|
| ● A+++ | Platinum | eg. Jovian Octagons ¹⁸ ; Garden of the Gods |
| ● A+ to A++ | Gold | eg. Big Sink ¹⁹ , Shiprock ²⁰ |
| ● A- to A | Silver | eg. Pine Mountain flux ²¹ , Upheaval Dome ²² |
| ● B+ to C+ | Bronze | eg. Grand Canyon, Knobs, Pilot Knobs ²³ |

Geology & Meteorology Are Not “Settled Science”

The ideas of uniformitarianism and anti-cataclysmic “settled science” are bunkish, to say the least. We’ve seen, in fact, that Global Warming (and its attached political agenda²⁴) are motivated not by science but anti-fuel money interests²⁵. The obsession with trace elements that cannot be verified on their effects in atmospheric or even basic sciences, is concerning. But more to the point, in soon to be posted MESSies, we shall see that the NOAA data machine learning algorithms are already making predictions along with the EGM line of thinking²⁶. Evidence has also been found of the karst region of Kentucky finally showing EGM connections in that it mysteriously *only exists* in Appalachia in the Pine Mountain Flux, in a narrow band²⁷. Which happens to be definitely connected with EGM via the Yelverton-Hall “Crooked smile” hypothesis. This was the same basic area that the NOAA databases were expecting more rain than occurred in areas that have known magnetic and gravity anomalies during predictions due to Hurricane Nicole (2022). Therefore, we can confidently say that even within mainstream’s own devices, definitely nothing is settled science. The very idea is anti-scientific. All models are simply trying to approach perfect completion.

The Importance of Physical Examination and Experiment

To get gold level evidence and data, one needs to take samples, verify samples, etc. You can *easily* disprove bad ideas. One video, and the author was able to show that there is no way Shiprock is 27 million years old²⁸. But actually proving what it is, how old it is, how it formed definitely, etc. will require samples and experiments to attempt to replicate the results. This could easily take 10 to 100 years. Someone nearby needs to do the real work, and go dozens of times, and pay for the samples, etc. Someone else with lab equipment might be capable of replicating the formation. Etc.

¹⁸

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

¹⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

²⁰ https://www.academia.edu/81402498/Trip_Report_Shiprock_and_Barringer_Crater

²¹ [MESS0020: GEO 2.21 - Andy Hall's Crooked Smile Hypothesis Proven by the Pine Mountain flux](#)

²² <https://www.iiisci.org/journal/pdv/sci/pdfs/ZA014LF20r.pdf>

²³ https://www.academia.edu/69494985/Plasmaglyphs_Part_1

²⁴ [MESS0031: POS Wave of Propaganda](#)

²⁵

https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

²⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology>

²⁷ [MESS0039: MET 2.31 - ; the proof the mainstream Change Theorist Data Learning Machines are Finding the Sa...](#)

²⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WtGz_hkJ3Ag

Electrogeometeorology - What is it?

The mixture of electrically formed geology²⁹ (GEO) with electrically controlled weather and solar-earth circuit controlled climate behaviors, into one science uniting the Spheres of Heaven and Earth³⁰, PEMS³¹, and HEGEME concepts, is together known as EGM.

→ It is **not** an excuse to use shapes you see patterns in to undo all geological history, and to make up bad theories, etc.

EGM 101 - Comparing Macrolytics with Lab Data

To avoid the problems Burke has; first you make a macroscopic observation. You note the potentials, and you develop macrolytic identifications³². From there you can compare the macrolytics with lab results, and/or you can search for microscopic evidence to replicate with lab experimentations, pulling data for comparison.

Ballistics & Geology; the Zamora Delusion

It is admirable that Zamora et al performed ballistic like experiments for their Carolina Bay theories³³. In a separate Ashes of Atlantis paper³⁴, the author will demonstrate exactly how mistaken these works are. But the short list of issues are:

- The ball-bearing is round, and this biases the shape; as no asteroids or comets are round.
- The velocity fired is sub-sonic.
- The material is loose and homogenous.
- The Bays are not of equal age to one another, separate by thousands of years in fluvial erosion.
- The Bays have walls that fill in ovals, without falling into the previous holes.³⁵
- The folded edges of the rims indicate *minor* carryover, not explosive chevrons.
- The Bays are not along a fanned or same vector, and some even show turning.
- The other impactor data there is really weak in tektite data.

The theory of his is another case of making facts to suit theories, and not theories to suit facts³⁶. It is one of the worst traits of the mainstream and of popular altstreamers. Both tend to ignore OOPArts³⁷, or visualize them according to weird and supremely improbable theories *first*. We have testimony for the

²⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/electrogeology>

³⁰ [MESS0023: MET 2.22 - The Spheres of Heaven in the HEGEME](#)

³¹

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

³² Large scale items that build other concepts through associative deductions (or inductions, as the case may warrant).

³³ https://www.academia.edu/69494986/Plasmaglyphs_Introduction

³⁴ [MESS0024: Ashes of Atlantis Part 2](#)

³⁵ Ibid. p16-18

³⁶ [MESS 2.10.1-.3 - MESS0025: Investigation - Sir Arthur's Gift](#)

³⁷ [MESS: The threefold Sacred Sciences](#)

thunderbolt hypothesis, and we have actual simulation³⁸ and geological “smoking guns”³⁹... the idea of giant chunks of ice being thrown out has no basis, and makes no physical⁴⁰ or ballistic sense. Besides that, the logic, vectors, and ballistics don’t work out, at all.

Conclusions

The author concludes that there is little to no support for Burke’s hypothesis, and it was performed contrary to proper scientific, EPEMC, and electrogeological standards. Also his strategy and manner of being interviewed was not conducive to the promotion of the EGM hypothesis. The author cannot but conclude that Burke’s ideas are simply bunkish, and this calls into question even his Great Lakes hypothesis, which at least has the value of evidence of the proximal and infamous Michigan “pure” copper deposits.

³⁸ <https://www.eixdelmon.com/peratt-instabilities-plasma-columns-z-pinch/>

³⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

⁴⁰ The temperatures at comet strike would vaporize all material to the atomic level and subatomic *immediately*.

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